

THE IMPORTANCE OF AUDIT IN THE BANKING SECTOR

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Abstract. *In the given article the importance of audit in the banking sector of the economy is discussed. The conducted research describes the essence and basic principles of bank audit.*

Keywords: *audit, accounting, banking sector, credit system.*

It is important to suggest that the banking sector is unique among sectors of the economy, since it plays an important role in ensuring financial stability and providing financial resources to the economy. In addition, banks have their own operating model. Supervisory authorities are primarily concerned with maintaining the stability of the banking system and increasing the safety and reliability of a number of banks in order to maintain confidence in the market and protect the interests of depositors. Therefore, in order to improve the effectiveness of control, supervisory authorities are very interested in the quality of bank inspections by external auditors. Establishing effective relationships with external auditors can also strengthen banking supervision. The main principles in the field of audit are independence, impartiality and honesty, professional competence and confidentiality of information.

Auditor independence is a principle of auditing, according to which the auditor must be free from any control and influence from the customer of audit services.

What is more important, auditor integrity is one of the general principles of auditing, based on the auditor's views on the concepts of fairness, justice, correctness and sincerity, the auditor's commitment to his professional duty and general ethical standards, a strict imperative. Confidentiality is an audit principle according to which the auditor should not disclose any information about the customer of audit services (the audited entity) obtained in the course of providing audit services. Auditing standards are international auditing standards and international quality control standards, international verification standards, international standards for the performance of assurance engagements, international standards for related services, published by the International Assurance and Auditing Standards Board of the International Federation of Accountants.

Besides that, strong internal controls, including the internal audit function and independent external audit, are part of effective corporate governance. In banks, they are also important for the safety and reliability of operations, and can facilitate mutually effective and constructive cooperation between bank management and banking supervisory authorities. Regular communication between banking supervisory authorities and internal and external auditors of banks improves the effectiveness of inspections and controls.

Bank audit is a system of control over compliance with banking control instructions and accounting procedures in a bank, including the auditor and the subject of the audit and other audit services.

Bank audit is divided into:

- mandatory and voluntary;
- internal and external.

Definitely, internal audit is carried out by a special department of the bank. External audit is carried out on a commercial basis (i.e. for a fee) by a professional market participant called an auditor.

The main tasks of bank audit:

- verification of the bank's financial statements;
- assessment of the financial condition of the bank;
- forecasting its activities;
- financial consulting.

The external auditor plans and performs the audit of the bank's financial statements to ensure that the financial statements are free from material misstatement, whether due to fraud or error, and that the financial statements are prepared, in all material respects, in accordance with the applicable framework.

For instance, the past 2019 coronavirus pandemic not only revealed deficiencies in risk management, control and governance processes in banks, but also revealed the need to improve the quality of external audits of banks.

External auditors of banks can play an important role in ensuring financial stability if they conduct high-quality bank audits, which contribute to increasing confidence in the financial statements of banks in the market.

By summarizing it should be suggested that high-quality bank checks also make a valuable contribution to the supervision process. The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision issues relevant regulations on external audit of banks in order to improve the quality of external audit of banks and the effectiveness of prudential supervision, which contributes to financial stability, which in turn contributes to achieving financial stability.

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